

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project was carried out by Ayoola Emmanuel ATITEBI with the matriculation number **KDU/FAPS/19/017** in the Department of Mathematical and Computing Sciences, Faculty of Applied Sciences, KolaDaisi University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to God Almighty: my guide, sustainer, and helper; and my family for their unconditional love and unwavering support in my life.

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ABSTRACT

Chatbots are computer programs designed to conduct textual or audible conversations with a single user. Website owners face a lot of issues ranging from providing customer support to engaging and interacting with users at various points in time. Hence, businesses waste a lot of capital and time, thereby, reducing their efficiency in the business sector. Mainly because there is so much a human can do when providing help, this is where a web-based chatbot system comes in. This work addresses the design, architecture, and applications of chatbots. It also discusses the evolution of chatbots, present a technical overview of the chatbot system and the technologies that support it, and address the applications and potential implications of chatbots in the wider world.

The web-based chatbot system developed in this work runs on the web. The system design and development comprise of a JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) file that stores user intents as well as the bot's responses to those intents. The system was written in Python and was powered by Python's backend framework, Flask. Flask is a lightweight Python web framework that provides useful tools and features for creating web applications in the Python language. The land-on-page for the application was developed using HTML5 and CSS3 and JavaScript. It was simply designed to be a descriptive site for the web software. The page was developed using Visual Studio code. Since the application was designed to be hosted on the web it is accessible to most devices.

In the case of this chatbot implementation, the program was run for a number of conversations and its results were recorded, mapping each conversation and the inputs within it to the probability that the chatbot got when assigning the input to some intent. The same process is then repeated while using the retraining method and recording the results with continual learning for the same conversations. All these results were analysed using a questionnaire designed using Google Forms. The questionnaire was filled out by 70 respondents. After the questionnaires were filled, a pie chart was drafted that calculates the percentage of individuals' opinions of the bot's responses. A very small amount of people had little to no experience with using chatbots to get responses to their queries. Most users reveal their previous experience with using chatbots to generate answers to several complex questions. The system was also deemed very valuable to website users of various levels as they found the chatbot system very informative and useful. Website users got access to valuable information with ease.

One of the technologies that have been making the most noise in the world of technology is Artificial Intelligence. AI ecosystem is vast with only a small part of it being explored today. As of now, Artificial Intelligence is perhaps the most interesting as well as challenging field of research. It has already proven itself for solving some major problems for mankind. This will further enhance human operations and reduce human errors that usually lead to day-to-day incidences.

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